

EBFMC25-OP-05 · Evaluation of the Relationship Between Nutrition and Sleep Status of Individuals Aged 65 and Over

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AUTHORS

Ziya Topaloglu
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2967-7106>

Arzu Ayraller
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5244-7571>

AFFILIATIONS

Giresun University, Faculty of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Giresun, Turkey

Giresun University, Faculty of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Giresun, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: This cross-sectional study examined the relationship between nutritional status and sleep quality in 65+ year-old patients receiving home healthcare services (HCS).

Methods: Nutritional status was assessed using the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA), and sleep quality was evaluated with the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI).

Results: We found 31.5% malnourished, 16.7% at risk, and 51.9% with normal nutrition. PSQI revealed 38.9% had poor sleep quality. A significant association was observed between malnutrition and worse sleep scores ($p = 0.0001$).

Conclusion: Results suggest nutritional interventions may improve sleep in elderly HCS patients.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Elderly, nutrition, sleep quality, malnutrition, home healthcare services, PSQI

INTRODUCTION

Old age is a significant chapter of life. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), individuals aged 65 and above are defined as elderly (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). Data from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK) indicate that the elderly population in Turkey increased from 6.89 million in 2017 to 8.45 million in 2022, accounting for 9.9% of the total population. Projections suggest this rate will rise to 12.9% by 2030 and 25.6% by 2080 (Turkish Statistical Institute [TÜİK], 2022).

Physiological and psychological changes accompany aging, leading to decreased body resistance and increased prevalence of chronic diseases. The growing elderly population, extended life expectancy, and chronic disease burden pose significant economic challenges. Accessible, high-quality, and sustainable health services are essential for managing chronic conditions (Kubat Bakir & Akin, 2019).

Technological advancements, social rights improvements, and rising healthcare costs have highlighted the importance of home health services globally and in Turkey. Implemented in Turkey since 2005, home health services provide nursing and long-term care by professionals (Aslan et al., 2018).

Sleep problems, prevalent in over 50% of the elderly, significantly impact quality of life. Common issues include insomnia, difficulty maintaining sleep, early awakenings, and non-restorative sleep. Factors such as retirement, loneliness, and physiological changes contribute to poor sleep quality (Palteki et al., 2021).

Nutrition and sleep disorders are critical yet understudied in the elderly. This study investigates the relationship between nutritional status and sleep quality in patients aged 65 and above registered in a Home Care Services.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained from Giresun Training and Research Hospital (Decision No: 05.06.23/04). Written consent was secured from participants, and data were collected voluntarily.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional, descriptive, and analytical study included 54 patients. Data were analyzed using SPSS 27.0, employing descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, and Kruskal-Wallis tests ($p < 0.05$).

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics software (Version 27.0). Descriptive statistics including frequencies (%), means, standard deviations, medians, and ranges (minimum-maximum) were calculated for all variables. Categorical variables were compared using the Chi-square test. The Shapiro-Wilk test assessed normality of continuous variables. For non-normally distributed variables, the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Study Design and Participants:

This cross-sectional descriptive-analytical study enrolled voluntary participants. A face-to-face administered sociodemographic questionnaire comprising 18 items collected data on:

- Demographic characteristics (age, gender, education level, marital status)
- Socioeconomic factors (employment status, Social Security Institution [SSI] coverage, income level)
- Family structure (parenthood status, number of children)
- Caregiving arrangements
- Health status (chronic disease presence, disease categories, polypharmacy defined as concurrent use of ≥ 4 medications)

Assessment Tools:

Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA);

The MNA, developed in 1989, evaluates nutritional status in elderly populations through multidimensional assessment of:

- Health status
- Functional capacity (mobility, independence)
- Cognitive function
- Disease burden
- Dietary intake patterns (Bauer et al., 2008)

Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI);

The PSQI (Buysse et al., 1989) is a validated 24-item instrument assessing sleep quality over a 1-month recall period. Eighteen items contribute to seven component scores (range: 0-3 each), with global scores calculated as follows:

- Good sleep quality: Total score < 5
- Poor sleep quality: Total score ≥ 5

RESULTS

Participants were predominantly female (75.9%), illiterate (25.9%), and unemployed (98.1%). Most (96.3%) had chronic diseases, and 81.5% reported polypharmacy. Malnutrition was significantly higher in neuropsychiatric and endocrine disease groups ($p = 0.027$, $p = 0.013$). Poor sleep quality (PSQI ≥ 5) was observed in 38.8%, with malnutrition linked to higher PSQI scores ($p = 0.0001$) (Tables 1–3).

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the nutritional status and sleep quality of patients aged over 65 years receiving HCS. As the first investigation to assess both parameters in HCS patients, it provides novel insights into this vulnerable population. In the study by Birgöl et al. (2022) conducted on the elderly in Nevşehir, 64.7% of the participants were women, whereas in the current study, this rate was 75.9%. Similarly, while 57.5% were married in Birgöl et al.'s (2022) study, the current study found a lower rate (46.3%). The illiteracy rate was 23.2% in their research, compared to 25.9% in this study. Additionally, while the chronic disease rate was 56.5% in Birgöl et al.'s (2022) study, it was significantly higher (96.3%) in the present study. When examining the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA) results, the prevalence of malnourished patients was 1.9% in Kaner's (2023) study, whereas 31.5% in the present study. Patients at risk of malnutrition constituted 38.5% of the sample in Kaner's (2023) study, compared to 16.7% in this study. Similarly, the proportion of patients with normal nutritional status was 59.6% in Kaner's (2023) study but 51.9% in the current findings. In Dolunay's (2023) study conducted in Edirne, where the nutrition of home health patients over 65 was evaluated, the frequency

of polypharmacy was 79.2%, whereas in this study, it was found to be 81.5%. When MNA results were evaluated, 14.2% were malnourished in Dolunay's (2023) study, compared to 31.5% in this study. While 49.4% were at risk of malnutrition in Dolunay's (2023) study, the current study found 16.7%. Additionally, 36.4% had normal nutritional status in Dolunay's (2023) study, whereas this study found 51.9%. Although the frequency of polypharmacy in this study was similar to Dolunay's (2023) findings, the rate of malnourished patients was higher. In the study conducted in Izmir in 2022, where the sleep of the elderly was evaluated, the frequency of polypharmacy was 57.2% (Şimşek Keskin et al., 2022), while in this study it was found to be 81.5%. The frequency of polypharmacy in our group was significantly higher than in the nursing home group. While the rate of impaired sleep quality (5 or more points on the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index [PSQI]) was 71.1% in Şimşek Keskin et al.'s (2022) study, it was 38.8% in this study, indicating better sleep quality among our participants. In the study conducted in Istanbul in 2022, which evaluated the nutritional levels and sleep of the elderly, 17.5% of the group were at risk of malnutrition (Uysal, 2022), compared to 16.7% in this study. While 82.5% had normal nutritional status in Uysal's (2022) study, this study found 51.9%. Additionally, impaired sleep quality (PSQI \geq 5) was reported in 55.7% of participants in Uysal's (2022) study, whereas this study found 38.8%. The highest PSQI score in Uysal's (2022) study was 19, compared to 14 in this study, suggesting that sleep quality was significantly worse in their sample. A negative statistical association was found between MNA and PSQI results in Uysal's (2022) study, which supports our findings. Further supporting our results, Zhao et al. (2021) found that poor sleep quality was significantly associated with malnutrition risk in older adults. Similarly, Jiang et al. (2023) demonstrated that good nutritional status reduces the risk of sleep disorders in adults aged 65 and older, aligning with our study's conclusions. Again, nutrition alone is affected by many factors and situations, and a person's sleep quality is also affected by many different situations. The effects of these and similar situations should not be ignored in studies on the elderly. As seen in this study, both chronic diseases and a person's sleep quality affect nutritional status. The malnutrition rate in the neuropsychiatric disease group in this study also supports other studies. Therefore, the risk of malnutrition is high in the neuropsychiatric patient group and this group should be evaluated especially in terms of malnutrition risk. In the literature, the nutritional status of individuals aged 65 and over is investigated from various aspects. However, there is no study investigating the nutrition and sleep status of geriatric individuals.

Limitations: Small sample size and single-center design limit generalizability. Confounding factors (e.g., comorbidities) were not fully controlled.

CONCLUSION

Nutritional status significantly impacts sleep quality in elderly home health patients. Regular screening for malnutrition and sleep disorders is recommended to improve care outcomes.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Arzu Ayraller

Giresun University, Faculty of Medicine

Department of Family Medicine

Giresun, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5244-7571>

ayraler7@hotmail.com